

Color of the plastic tube (blue, yellow, pink, and orange) had no significant effect on larval mortality and moth emergence. A few moths, mostly larger-size females, died inside the tubes. The larger moths need tubes a bit wider (5-6 mm). Tube walls should be thin (not more than 0.3-0.4 mm), so that larvae can cut a hole before pupation. ■

***Chilo auricilius* Dudgeon (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae), the correct name for the dark-headed stem borer (SB) found in the Philippines**

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We investigated the *Chilo* SB complex in rice, maize, sorghum, and sugarcane. Tillers were dissected and larvae found were reared individually in 20- × 3.5-cm tcst tubes. Pupae were transferred to plastic petri dishes for moth emergence. The abdomen of each moth was cut, cleared in a hot 10% solution of KOH, and washed with distilled water.

In 1,316 samples from throughout the Philippines, we found *C. suppressalis* (Walker) and *C. auricilius*, but not *C. polychrysus* (Meyrick). All larvae identified earlier as dark-headed SB were the gold-fringed borer *C. auricilius*. *C. auricilius* comprised 73% of the *Chilo* SB found in upland rice and 97-100% of those found in maize, sorghum, and sugarcane (Table 1).

The morphological similarity of the larvae and moths of the two species had led to earlier, erroneous records of *C. polychrysus* in the Philippines. Similar

Table 1. Composition of *Chilo* reared from 4 agricultural crops.

Crop	Borers examined (no.)	Composition (%)	
		<i>C. auricilius</i>	<i>C. suppressalis</i>
Rice			
Upland	482	73	27
Wetland	171	17	83
Maize	364	97	3
Sorghum	278	100	0
Sugarcane	21	100	0
Total	1316		

Table 2. Comparative moth morphology, life history, and host plant range of *C. auricilius* and *C. polychrysus*.^a

Criterion	<i>C. polychrysus</i> ^b	<i>C. auricilius</i>
Forewing of moth (see figure)	Terminal dots and subterminal line indistinct; subterminal line white with a few silvery scales; median line distinct, oblique and pale yellow brown; discal dot highly reduced; fringe slightly glossy; hindwing whitish to dirty cream	Terminal dots large; subterminal line represented by a row of metallic scales, and close to the apical margin; median line metallic line subterminal; discal dot visible; fringe shiny golden; hindwing light brown
Larva (see figure)	Dorsal setae D ₁ and D ₂ in the VIII abdominal segment nearly equidistant from dorsal line; adfrontal area of head same in color as the fronto-clypeal area	Seta D ₁ of VIII abdominal segment closer to the dorsal line than seta D ₂ ; adfrontal area of head paler than fronto-clypeal area
Development (d)	30-44	37-42
Egg incubation	4-7	6-8
Larva	20-30	22-24
Prepupa	No data	1
Pupa	6-7	8-9
Fecundity (no. of eggs/female)	73-488	5-233
Longevity (d)	2-5	6-9
Host plant range		
<i>Cyperus digitatus</i> Roxb.	+	-
<i>Dactyloctenium aegyptium</i> P. Beauv.	-	+ ^c
<i>Echinochloa colona</i> (L.)	-	+ ^c
<i>E. crus-galli</i> ssp. <i>hispidula</i> (Retz.) Honda	+	-
<i>E. frumentacea</i> Link.	-	+ ^c
<i>E. stagnina</i> (P. Beauv.)	-	+ ^c
<i>Eleusine indica</i> Gaertn.	-	+ ^c
<i>Erianthus munja</i> Roxb.	-	+ ^c
<i>Hemarthria</i> (= <i>Rotboellia</i>) <i>compressa</i> (L.f.) R. Br.	-	+ ^c
<i>Hymenache pseudointerrupta</i> C. Muell.+	-	-
<i>Ischaemum rugosum</i> Salisb.	-	+ ^c
<i>Leptochloa chinensis</i> (L.) Nees	-	+
Millet (name not specified)	+	-
<i>Oryza sativa</i> L.	+	+
<i>Pennisetum purpureum</i> Schum.	-	+ ^c
<i>Saccharum officinarum</i> L.	-	+
<i>S. spontaneum</i> L.	-	+ ^c
<i>Sacciolepis interrupta</i> (Willd.)	-	+ ^c
<i>Sacciolepis myosuroides</i> (R. Br.) A. Camus	+	+ ^c
<i>Schlerostachya fusca</i> (Roxb.) A. Camus	-	+ ^c
<i>Scirpus grossus</i> L.f.	+	-
<i>Setaria italica</i> (L.) P. Beauv.	+	-
<i>S. palliolo-fusca</i> (Schum.) Stapf & C.E. Hubb.	+	-
<i>Sorghum bicolor</i> Moench	-	+
<i>S. halepense</i> (L.) Pers.	-	+
<i>Sporobolus diander</i> P. Beauv.	-	+
<i>S. indicus</i> R. Br.	-	+ ^c
<i>Triticum aestivum</i> L.	-	+
<i>Zea mays</i> L.	+	+
<i>Zizania aquatica</i> L.	+	-
<i>Z. lotifolia</i> Turcz.	+	-

^a+ = recorded host, - = no recorded host. ^bSource: Banerjee, S.N. and L.M. Pramanik, 1967. The lepidopterous stalk borers of rice and their life cycles in the tropics. pp. 103-126. In: The Major Insect Pests of the Rice Plant. The International Rice Research Institute. Johns Hopkins Press, Baltimore, Maryland. 729 p.; Anonymous. 1967. Rice Production Training Manual: Rice Insect Pests. IRRI, Los Baños. 182 p. ^cSource: Chaudhary, J.P. and S.K. Sharma, 1986. The stalk borer, *Chilo auricilius*. pp. 135-150. In: Sugarcane Entomology in India. Sugarcane Breeding Institute. Indian Council of Agricultural Research. Coimbatore, India. 564 p.

confusion may exist in countries where their distributions overlap: India, Thailand, Indonesia, and Malaysia.

Table 2 compares *C. auricilius* and *C.*

polychrysus on the basis of morphology, life history, and host plant range.

IRRI will accept *Chilo* moths for further comparison and identification. ■